

Knowledge Processing in Intelligent Systems

J.UCS Special Issue

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This special issue of the Journal of Universal Computer Science contains selected and extended papers presented at the *First International Symposium on Agent and Multi-agent Systems: Technology and Applications (KES-AMSTA 2007)*, which was successfully held in Wroclaw, Poland, 31 May - June 1, 2007. This symposium is the first event in the symposium series on Agent and Multi-agent Systems, chaired by N.T. Nguyen, and supported by KES International and Wroclaw University of Technology. The aim of KES-AMSTA series is to provide an internationally respected forum for scientific research in the technologies and applications of agent and multi-agent systems. The issue also includes several invited papers from other authors.

We cordially thank the reviewers for their valuable reviews which guarantee the high quality of the accepted papers. Special thanks go to the authors for their contributions to this special issue. Finally, we would like to thank Professor Hermann Maurer, the Managing Editor of J.UCS, and the Editorial Team for their support in editing this issue.

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June 2008